

Small state's anticipation of institutional change: Effects of the looming Brexit in the area of the CSDP and internal market

Brexit will change the balance of power in the European Union. All countries will have to adjust it, but the issue is more pressing for small member states that are more dependent on international organisations than big states. This article studies how the institutional setting affects a small state's preparations for Brexit in the area of common security and defence policy and internal market. Contrary to the theoretical expectations, it shows that the Czech Republic, the small state under scrutiny, has invested more effort into a preventive adjustment in the supranational internal market policy than to the CSDP. This result is explained by the existence of alternative institutional frameworks that are expected to mitigate the impact of Brexit on EU's security and defence policy. It also suggests that while small states profit from the existence of strong institutions, they also face the risk of unmitigated impact when these institutions change.

Keywords: small state, Brexit, adaptation, CSDP, internal market.

Introduction

One of the key member states of the European Union, the United Kingdom, is leaving the club. While not one of the founding countries, the UK has left an immense imprint on the current shape of European integration. When it leaves, it will leave behind a void that will be felt throughout the EU and have a significant impact on many EU policies and EU politics. As rational choice institutionalism suggests, institutions influence states' behaviour because they shape the structure in which the states can pursue their interests (cf. Hall and Taylor 1996). Brexit will inevitably change the power structure in the EU.

All EU member states will need to adjust to the new balance of power within the Union after Brexit. Germany, for example, needs to reconsider the functioning of the German-French engine that has been for a long time balanced by the more sceptical British (Rittlemeyer 2017) and take over more responsibilities regarding leadership in liberalising the single market and in foreign policy (Traugott 2018). France, worried about becoming the

only country with full-scale capabilities in the EU, struggles to keep the UK as close to EU security policy as possible, such as through the proposed European Intervention Initiative (Koenig 2018). The challenge is, however, more urgent for smaller EU member states.

Small states are generally considered irrelevant by IR scholars because they cannot influence the international system (Maass 2016). That is why rule-based systems, such as the EU, help smaller countries thrive (cf. Wivel *et al.* 2014). The literature recognises that small states can have an impact on policy results and focuses on the means and channels they use (cf. Bunse 2009, Haugevik 2017, Panke 2012, Smed and Wivel 2017, Weiss 2017).

Nevertheless, small states are ‘structurally disadvantaged’ even in the most orderly settings (Panke 2010). Their threats are less credible and their side-offers less valuable than those of big countries (cf. Hayes-Renshaw and Wallace 2006, p. 252, Thomson 2011, p. 212ff). They have more limited outside options, which makes them more dependent on the negotiation results (cf. Moravcsik 1993, p. 500, Voeten 2001). That makes a choice between autonomy and integration vis-à-vis the EU particularly pressing for smaller EU member states (Haugevik and Rieker 2017). As the smaller countries do not have full autonomy, they need to be very careful when adopting a position towards new initiatives and when the environment changes profoundly (cf. Hedling and Brommesson 2017).

Small member states are like canaries in a coal mine – they will feel the impact of any change early on. They are, therefore, very likely to prepare strategically to make the best of the new opportunities or to dodge the looming problems (Bishop and Clegg 2018, Wivel and Thorhallsson 2018). Their reaction will not be equally strong in all policy areas. On some issues, such as the Economic and Monetary Union, the impact of Brexit will only be indirect, because the UK has not been a Eurozone member and even has had a permanent opt-out. In other areas, the UK has been much more involved and sometimes crucial in the development and steering of the policy, such as in defence policy.

From the perspective of the small member states, the institutional differences are crucial. In supranational policies, the primary law boundaries, the established legal framework, and the jurisprudence of the EU Court of Justice will dampen any impact of Brexit. Small states can often rely on the Commission to maintain the long-term direction and provide stability in policy areas where it plays an important role, even with a different balance of power in the Council (cf. Geurts 1998). In intergovernmental areas, by contrast, small countries are much more exposed to the policy leadership of the large countries (cf. Sjursen 2011, Smith 2004). Although nominally equal and able to cast a veto, small states cannot afford it as often as the big states in practice (Tallberg 2008, p. 691). This is visible in the case of the EU security and defence policy, which has been primarily shaped by the three big countries, the UK, France, and Germany (Howorth 2000).

This paper builds on the claims reviewed above and posits that small EU member states' preparations to Brexit will differ in different policy areas. It picks two very different policies – the internal market and the common security and defence policy (CSDP) – and expects that a limited pressure on policy adaptation will exist in the area of the internal market, while it will be much stronger in the area of security. This is in line with the theoretical expectation of the impact of the supranational institutions, which have the potential to dampen the impact of the changing balance of power in the Council in areas where they play a substantial role. This expectation is further augmented by the fact that security policy, of which the CSDP is a part, is a particularly sensitive area for small states (Wivel *et al.* 2014, Maass 2016). This paper aims to test this expectation on a single case study of the Czech Republic. It expects the Czech representatives to re-visit Czech EU policies in the light of Brexit and to observe higher activity in the CSDP than on the issue of the internal market. The preparations may take place at two levels, political and administrative. The role of the political level is to set priorities, exert leadership, and

communicate the Czech position to EU partners and the domestic population. The role of the administrative level, in turn, is to propose specific policy changes and to adapt to the new institutional environment at the EU level.

The Czech Republic is an apt case to study. It has relied on the cooperation with the United Kingdom in both policy areas, and as a result, it will be influenced significantly by the UK's departure. Czechia has shared the cautious British approach to the development of CSDP and the emphasis on NATO ties. The political alignment spilled over to structural cooperation. The Czech military served under the British command in most overseas operations, including Bosnia, Afghanistan, and Iraq. There is a British liaison officer at the Czech defence ministry, a British Military Advisory Training Team offers courses in the Czech army's training facilities in Vyškov, and other projects touch upon various aspects of security policy and military preparedness (cf. British Embassy Prague 2016). On the internal market, Czechia has belonged to the most vocal advocates of further deepening and liberalisation (cf. Šlosarčík 2011), the position usually championed by the United Kingdom. The commitment to further liberalisation has been a constant in all governments' programmes ever since, each time with a specific focus given by the ideological flavour of the government. The Czechia has been a member of a like-minded group promoting further liberalisation, which has been led by the United Kingdom, and featured other smaller countries, such as the Netherlands and Sweden (cf. Weiss 2017). The Czech Republic is also expected to be one of the five most affected EU countries in case of the EU-UK trade falling back to the WTO option (Chen *et al.* 2018). The UK has belonged to the most important destinations for Czech export, and British companies have been significant investors in Czechia (Beneš *et al.* 2018, p. 15f, Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Czech Republic 2018).

Also, there has been significant political cooperation between the UK and Czechia with the Czech civic democrats acting as one of the critical partners for British conservatives in their bid to form a new political group in the European Parliament.

The data for this research were collected in summer 2018, and the text was put together and revised between autumn 2018 and spring 2019. The withdrawal agreement and political declaration concluded in November 2018 confirmed that the United Kingdom would not be able to participate in EU decision-making after Brexit. At the time of writing, the United Kingdom still was an EU member, and the result of the Brexit process remained unclear. It does not matter, however, whether and how the UK leaves the EU for the argument followed here. The article is interested in how a small state anticipates the future change in power distribution and prepares for it in different policy areas.

The analysis draws on available public documents produced by the Czech government, media statements by Czech politicians, and relevant parliamentary documents. There is, however, a very limited written account of the Czech policy so far. Particularly when evaluating the preparations on the administrative level, the paper builds on semi-structured interviews with officials from central state institutions, the Office of the Government, Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Ministry of Defence, and Ministry of Industry and Trade.

The article concludes that, against all expectations, the Czech Republic has been more active in preparing for Brexit in the internal market area than in security and defence. The difference is particularly striking at the administrative level, but can also be traced at the political level. The main reason is found in the existence of alternative institutional frameworks that limit the expected impact of the British departure on the balance of power in the EU, despite the formal exit from the decision-making mechanisms.

In what follows, the paper first briefly shows that the British decision to leave has already had a significant impact on EU security and defence policy and a minimal impact on the development of the internal market. It then offers a brief account of the immediate Czech reaction to the Brexit referendum. Next, the Czech reaction to and preparation for Brexit are analysed in detail on political and on administrative levels. The final part concludes and asks what the findings mean for our understanding of the small state's position in an international organisation.

Effects of the looming Brexit so far

The United Kingdom has long been a critical enabler and actor of the European Union's security and defence policy and one of the biggest obstacles to its further development. On the one hand, the UK is one of only two European countries able to deploy close to the full spectrum of military capabilities (Martill and Sus 2018, p. 2). It provides around 40 per cent of Europe's total defence research and development budget (Besch 2018, p. 11), valuable intelligence for the EU's action abroad, not to mention the permanent seat at the UN Security Council. On the other hand, the UK has never seen the EU's common security and defence policy as a priority. The British participation in the CSDP missions and operations has been relatively low (House of Lords European Union Committee 2018, p. 33ff) and the UK vetoed further institutional development of the CSDP, particularly the establishment of a standing military headquarters (cf. Kempin and Mawdsley 2013).

The British exit from the European Union will inevitably have a lasting impact on the EU's security and defence. Depending on the final deal between the UK and the EU-27, the EU will have to learn how to plug in the British (Besch 2018) who will become a third country according to the EU law, or how to proceed without their capabilities and clout. At the same time, Brexit offers an opportunity to further develop EU security cooperation in

areas, where the British veto or potential veto effectively blocked any debate (Major and Mölling 2017, cf. Pannier 2018).

Indeed, the CSDP has already moved forward, even if the UK has not left the Union yet. In the framework of the EU Global Strategy implementation, several new initiatives have been proposed at the EU level that collectively aim at increasing the EU's defence capabilities and deepening cooperation among EU member states in the area of military research, development, and procurement. These initiatives represent the EU's reaction to the changing security environment, most notably the instability in the EU's neighbourhood, the Russian annexation of Crimea, and the increased US pressure for a more significant burden sharing. While not induced by Brexit, many have been enabled by the fact that the UK plans to leave. In 2017, the EU finally established the Military Planning and Conduct Capability within the EU Military Staff structures, an EU military headquarters that had been blocked by the UK several times in the past. While it is not a full-fledged command centre and should only take over command and planning of EU non-executive operations (notably training missions), the MPCC is a qualitative leap forward for the CSDP (Tardy 2017). At the same time, the Council and the Commission launched three other inter-related initiatives the European Defence Fund, the Coordinated Annual Review on Defence, and the Permanent Structured Cooperation (Fiott *et al.* 2017). They should increase collective spending on defence-related research and development among the member states by identifying common needs, defining priority projects to which more countries subscribe, and covering part of the costs from the EU budget. Potentially, this could lead to more and more collective spending on defence in the EU member states as well as an increase in interoperability among their militaries. While remaining short of an actual 'European Army' so often referred to by politicians (cf. Menon 2015), the new initiatives constitute a cautious leap forward in European defence cooperation that may have seemed to lose its drive lately. Last but not

least, the President of the Commission recently announced that he would be proposing the introduction of qualified majority decisions in foreign and security area, where the treaties so allow, including some parts of the CSDP.

There has been a much more limited impact in the internal market area so far. Most initiatives that are currently on the table had already been discussed before June 2016, be it the single digital market or the energy union. The bulk of the Commission's activity has its origin in the pledge to revisit the current legislation within the framework of the regulatory fitness and performance reviews (European Commission 2014). This is visible in the Commission's work programmes adopted after the British referendum where the continuity and streamlining prevails and no new flagship initiatives appear comparable to the defence area (cf. European Commission 2016, 2017, 2018).

Thus, the impact of the looming Brexit corresponds with the theoretical expectation so far that there would be potential for change in an intergovernmental policy and lesser impact in supranational areas where the EU institutions exert a higher influence over the agenda and conduct of the policies.

Czech reaction to the British referendum

In the most general terms, the Czech reaction to the results of the Brexit referendum was not substantially different from other EU countries. Most politicians declared their regret over the British decision and their hope that there would remain room for close cooperation between the EU and the UK in future. They focused mainly on the EU itself and on what Brexit meant for the EU's legitimacy and future. Only fringe and extremist parties' representatives welcomed the result and called for the Czech Republic to follow the UK out of the EU (Novinky.cz 2016).

The shock of Brexit initiated an unprecedented cross-party dialogue about Czech interests in the upcoming negotiations. The Czech EU policy has traditionally suffered from a lack of interest among party leaders and the inability to define national interest that any government, irrespective of party affiliation and ideology, could promote (cf. Beneš 2017). Regularly, internal politicking trumped national interest, such as in the case of the unexpected fall of the government in the middle of the Czech Council presidency in 2009. After June 2016, however, the prime minister initiated a dialogue of all political parties represented in the lower chamber of the Czech parliament to identify the Czech priorities for the Brexit negotiations and in the debate on the future reform of the EU jointly. The common declaration of the party leaders that resulted from this dialogue pinpointed the rights of Czech citizens in the UK, maintaining economic ties, and cooperation on security as the key issues (Joint Statement of the Leaders of Political Parties Represented in the Parliament on the Negotiations on the United Kingdom's withdrawal from the European Union 2017).

More practically, the Czech government established a working group for Brexit at the Office of the Government immediately after the British referendum (Czech Radio 2016). It brought together representatives from all sectoral ministries to coordinate the Czech position in negotiations at the EU level, to monitor the progress of EU negotiators, and to timely identify issues that could arise for Czech businesses and citizens, as well as to guarantee the preparedness of the Czech administration for Brexit. The working group serves as the domestic hub for the Czech representation in the Ad hoc Working Party on Article 50, which the Council established in May 2017 to supervise the European Commission in the negotiations with the United Kingdom.

Czech preparations in the area of security and defence policy

Political level

At the political level, the Czech representatives have emphasised the need for a common EU-27 approach to the negotiations from the very beginning. A quick resolution of the post-referendum uncertainty was the primary concern (Hruška 2016). Security then became one of three priority topics identified by the Czech Republic before the beginning of the negotiation with the United Kingdom (see above). This reflects both the relative weight of the UK in the EU security policy and security policy in Europe in general, and the contacts between the Czechs and the British in this area.

Since then, however, Czech politicians seem to have ignored the issue altogether. Security and defence do not feature in any further declarations or statements by leading political figures. Following the meetings with the EU negotiator or European Council summits, the prime ministers have stressed the indivisibility of the four freedoms and the rights of Czech citizens in the UK repeatedly, but they never flagged the security cooperation again, with the exception of the security of information and data (Czech Information Agency 2016, Vlada.cz 2018).

There has been a robust Czech involvement in the on-going debate on the deepening of European cooperation in security and defence at the same time. The Czech government hosted a high-level conference on the future of the European security and defence just two days after the Commission had announced the creation of the European Defence Fund. The conference featured Commission President Juncker, High Representative Mogherini, commissioners Katainen and Bieńkowska involved in launching the fund, and the European Defence Agency chief executive Domecq, as well as foreign and defence ministers from various EU countries, including France, Slovakia, and Greece. To show that strengthening of EU defence would not constitute a threat to transatlantic relations, a NATO Deputy

Secretary-General was one of the keynote speakers beside Juncker, Mogherini, and Prime Minister Sobotka (Government of the Czech Republic 2017). Later on, the Czech government also actively contributed to the debate on the launch of the Permanent Structured Cooperation (PESCO), co-signing the 4+4 letter to the High Representative, together with four big (Germany, France, Italy, Spain) and three other small member states (Belgium, Finland, the Netherlands) (Fiott *et al.* 2017, p. 25). Despite the change of the government in December 2017, Czechia continued to support the deepening of European defence cooperation, building on significant personal continuity and given the fact that the new government, which failed to win the vote on confidence, did not revisit any major strategic documents.

However, the anticipation of Brexit did not play a significant role in the Czech support to PESCO. Czech politicians ‘sought a shift of defence cooperation to a higher level qualitatively’ (Stropnický 2017), but connected it firmly to the protection of European borders and with crisis management in the countries that had become the source of main migration flows to Europe in the Czech discourse (cf. Sobotka 2016). In addition, the Czech enthusiasm can be understood as an attempt to present oneself as a constructive partner in an area, which was not controversial among the voters (Interview #1, Interview #4), thus improving the tarnished Central European image after the migration crisis. The activities at the administrative level further support such an interpretation.

Administrative level

In Czechia, foreign and defence ministries jointly formulate the country’s security and defence policy, with the contribution of the office of the government and interior ministry where appropriate. While the foreign ministry, more specifically the security policy department, shapes the general framework and coordinates the Czech behaviour in NATO, the EU, and the OSCE, the ministry of defence manages military capabilities and drafts the

Czech armaments policy. Office of the Government is responsible for the overall coordination of Czech European policy, including positions on Brexit (cf. Karlas *et al.* 2013; Knutelská 2013).

For the administrative level, the domestic political instability in 2017-18 meant (elections, a failed attempt to form a government) a lack of political guidance, but it also provided stability of the position. Civil servants formulated policies along the lines of the latest documents adopted by the government (Interview #1), which meant the general framework of the Czech foreign policy concept (Government of the Czech Republic 2015a), the broad EU strategy (Government of the Czech Republic 2015b), and the guidelines on CSDP from December 2016 (Government of the Czech Republic 2016). As a result, the Czech Republic continued to support an ambitious and inclusive PESCO but failed to make a significant contribution to the first round of projects. Czechs half-heartedly proposed three projects because of a last-minute political demand, but none of them was prepared and pre-negotiated enough to be successful (which was generally accepted with relief at the defence ministry) (Interview #2). In the end, Czechia got involved as a participant in three projects – on military mobility, European medical command, and training mission competence centre. Similarly, the approach to the French-led European Intervention Initiative was to observe, but not to get involved yet. The general understanding among the civil service was that the military was unable to provide a sufficient number of soldiers for overseas operations, which limited the capacity of the country to participate more actively (Interview #1). Overall, the Czech engagement in the new EU defence initiatives could be described as nominally enthusiastic, but practically limited.¹

The anticipated Brexit did not change anything at all in this respect, and both the foreign and the defence ministries shared the view that there was no need to re-think the Czech security policy (Interview #2, Interview #4). This view was based on two arguments.

Firstly, while the EU had featured in all Czech strategic documents, most thinking about defence built on NATO and NATO-provided frameworks. As the United Kingdom was not leaving NATO, there was no need to worry or revisit any policies. There might be some practical problems expected, such as how to replace the experienced British personnel in operational planning for CSDP missions, but there was no substantive change strategically. Secondly, there was a general expectation that the UK would remain closely engaged in the CSDP after Brexit (an expectation which is also built into the political declaration signed by the EU and the British government). The EU-27 and the UK see the same threats as relevant and face the same instability in the current security environment. External factors push the UK and the EU even closer together, most notably president Trump's disinterest in Africa and other issues, which are not directly linked to the US interests, but may be highly important for Europeans. Also, the EU is not the only framework through which the UK is involved. There are bilateral and extra-treaty initiatives, such as the Lancaster House Treaty and the European Intervention Initiative, which would keep the UK firmly attached. Finally, yet importantly, there was a general will among the member states to ensure British participation, even if there were clear red lines, such as the need for a European institutional and decision-making autonomy (Interview #3).

There is a risk of complacency, and the Czech civil service was aware that the Brexit process could nosedive. While there was no serious worry about complications in the security policy area, there was an awareness among security policy professionals that a spillover of a bad will could hamper the ability of the UK and the EU to cooperate on security in future (Interview #1). Notably, severe fallouts over the Irish border, the future of mutual trade relations, or the citizens' rights could poison any form of cooperation for many years to come. The Czech Republic prepared for no such scenario, believing that the odds were too little and the common interest too big to substantiate the investment of time and effort. There

had been cooperation with other allies in place already before the Brexit referendum, particularly with Germany, France, and Poland. The loss of the British ally, even if it was to happen, was therefore not expected to cause any major problem. There was no mention of Brexit or the UK in the Czech framework positions to the European Defence Fund and the European Defence Industrial Development Programme (Ministry of Defence of the Czech Republic 2017a, 2017b).

To sum up, Czech politicians and civil servants did not feel the need to re-assess the country's approach to the CSDP in the wake of the Brexit referendum. The positive Czech attitude to the new initiatives stemmed instead from the country's effort to improve its image in the EU after the migration fall out than from a need to adapt to a new distribution of power. Also, Brexit was not considered as a critical issue in the security area given the plethora of other institutionalised ties that bind Britain to the rest of European countries and the common strategic interests and threat perception.

Czech preparations in the area of the internal market

Political level

Unlike security and defence, the internal market did not disappear from the statements of Czech politicians about Brexit. In particular, the indivisibility of the four freedoms was important for the Czechs and worth mentioning on many occasions (Czech Information Agency 2016, Vlada.cz 2018). Similarly, the parliament repeatedly emphasised its support to the common EU position in the negotiations and the need to not decouple the individual freedoms from each other (Výbor pro evropské záležitosti PS PČR 2017, cf. Balounová 2017).

Czech politicians coordinated the position with partners from other member states. A coordination meeting of the Visegrád Group representatives, followed by the meeting of V4

foreign ministers and prime ministers, took place just a couple of days after the referendum in the UK (Visegrad Group 2016b). At Bratislava summit in September 2017 where heads of states and governments of EU-27 gathered to reinvigorate European integration after Brexit, another V4 joint declaration called for liberalisation across the four freedoms focused on higher competitiveness of the EU (Visegrad Group 2016a).

Apart from the general statements, however, there was a minimal political activity on the issue of the internal market. Generally, Czech politicians were waiting for the EU representatives to negotiate the withdrawal agreement. The rest was business as usual without the need to revisit any strategic documents or priorities. Czech policy on the internal market remained guided by the strategic document adopted in November 2015 (Government of the Czech Republic 2015c). In a nutshell, the government continued to support further liberalisation of the EU internal market, mainly focusing on the environment for small and medium enterprises. The relative silence with which the political level treated the impact of Brexit on the internal market contrasts with the activity of the administration.

Administrative level

From the administrative perspective, the internal market is a vast area, which is challenging to manage due to the concentration of actors, interests, and forms of governance. There are differences in the approach of the individual member states to the internal market in general due to their varying historical legacies (Schmidt 2013). Moreover, different interests are stemming from the ideological leaning of individual governments as well as from the structure of the national economies. The Ministry of Industry and Trade manages the bulk of the internal market-related policies in the Czech Republic.

Ministry officials considered Brexit a double challenge. In the short term, there was anxiety to maintain a common position among the EU-27 and not to compromise the unity of

the internal market and the four freedoms. A concession on these topics, while advantageous in the short term, was considered highly problematic in the longer term, threatening the internal market as a whole. The UK had been one of the key trade partners for the Czech Republic, and there were many Czech companies doing business with British counterparts. The ministry did not have the full overview of the Czech-British trade ties, and as a result, it concentrated on building up communication channels between the ministry officials and individual businesses. CzechTrade, a ministry-funded agency supporting Czech companies abroad, organised monthly roundtables where companies could obtain information and raise specific issues that ministry officials could later flag in Brussels. Also, business federations' representatives participated in the working group on Brexit organised by the office of the government. They could distribute all the information obtained there to their members. The communication with the companies should ensure that everybody was prepared for the Brexit date and as little trade disruption as possible took place. One of the concrete results of the dialogue was, for example, a realisation that one of the largest Czech companies had had some of its product certifications from the UK. The ministry was able to pass the information to the Commission and to find a satisfactory solution (Interview #5).

Czech civil servants considered the long-term effect of Brexit to be more important than the temporary difficulties of the day, however. They expected Brexit to weaken the liberal camp in the Council and to change the balance of power in the negotiations over the future of the internal market significantly. Even though the UK had not left the EU yet, the looming Brexit already influenced the negotiations and made it difficult for the like-minded liberal group of states to make their voice heard on the further liberalisation of services, reportedly. The UK had been the acknowledged leader of the group that usually spoke in Council negotiations with the smaller countries supporting the British position. With the UK restrained in its contributions to the negotiations over the future shape of the internal market,

there was no other big state left in the group (Interview #3). The remaining countries started negotiating with Germany to take the lead, but Germany is often unable to vocalise certain positions, because of its complicated domestic structure or political considerations (Interview #5). As a result, there was major anxiety about the future development of the internal market and particularly the possibility of further liberalisation.

To sum up, Czech representatives at both levels recognised the internal market as one of the priorities for Czech policy on Brexit. At the political level, the general approach remained constant, and Brexit loomed as a potential threat to the cohesiveness of the internal market only. At the administrative level, by contrast, Brexit was considered a significant strategic change with an impact on the future shape of the internal market. It was seen to restrict the room for further liberalisation and to weaken the like-minded liberal group in Council negotiations significantly. As a result, Czechs took concrete steps in cooperation with their allies to minimise the impact of future Brexit and to adjust to the shift in the power distribution in the Council.

Conclusions

Brexit will constitute a change in the balance of power in the EU. This change calls for a reaction by small member states, including Czechia. This paper has reviewed the Czech preparations for Brexit at political and administrative levels and sought to confirm that they differ according to the institutional setup of respective policy areas. The theory suggests that small states would react more strongly in security and defence policy where no supranational institutions may soften the impact of the UK's exit than in internal market matters. Indeed, the anticipation of Brexit has already contributed to a significant development in the CSDP area, while no such movement has been visible in the internal market policy.

The evidence presented here defies the expectations, however. The looming Brexit did not keep Czech politicians busy with adjusting Czech security and defence policy, nor feel the ministry officials any urge to prepare for a different setting in negotiations. Czech involvement in the new CSDP initiatives was largely nominal and driven by the effort to improve the country's image in the EU following the catastrophic conduct during the migration crisis. By contrast, the anticipation of Brexit and the diminished activity of the UK in Council negotiations in the internal market area provoked a re-evaluation of future opportunities at the administrative level, including a search for new allies. What could account for this result?

It seems that the nature of the impending British departure plays a vital role. Indeed, the institutions change the states' behaviour and may provide shelter for smaller members by binding the bigger ones in a net of rules and procedures. In the case of Brexit, however, the institutionalised environment of internal market policy also restricts the options for the small states to avoid the full impact of British departure. The single institutional setting governing the single market ensures that the UK will be disappearing from the deliberations entirely when exiting the EU. On security and defence where the policy is not as well institutionalised, by contrast, the UK will remain part of the negotiations through its presence in the wide web of institutions beyond the EU, such as NATO and a plethora of bilateral agreements.

Several general conclusions can be drawn that are relevant for the broader literature on small states and international institutions. Firstly, the research underlines the relative importance of large states. The Czech activity in the internal market area shows that even in the highly institutionalised setting that should provide stability for the small states, a unilateral decision by a big country makes all the difference to the small state's perception of the situation. We can only assume that a similar decision to leave by one of the small EU

members would not provoke such a strong reaction. This reveals how the small states' structural disadvantage, referred to in the literature, is manifested in practice.

Secondly, the results highlight the importance of institutional context for an analysis of institutional change. In the case of Czechia's preparations for Brexit, the existence of alternative institutional frameworks, what economists would call a substitute good, has played a more important role than the character of the policy in question and its institutional setting. As there are substitute frameworks in case of defence cooperation, Brexit did not require significant adjustment. In internal market policy, however, where there are no ready substitutes, the expected change in power balance had to be tackled.

Thirdly, this research puts into perspective the general claim in the literature that small states profit from strong international institutions, which protect them from the Hobbesian world of international relations and provide them with influence. Strong institutionalisation and lock-in, which is characteristic for EU's supranational policies, bind all member states to the single negotiation framework. Thus, they effectively erase the bigger states' key advantage of having a more viable outside option. The open dominance of the big states in the intergovernmental policies of the European Union, such as the CSDP, and their reliance on solutions outside the treaty framework, such as the European Intervention Initiative and the Lancaster House Treaty, confirms this view. While this may all be true in general terms and good weather, ceding more power to an international organisation, such as the EU, also means accepting more risk in times of abrupt institutional change and a shift in the internal balance of power. Small states do gain more stability through a powerful EU most of the time, but they are putting all eggs in one basket. When a hole appears in the basket, like the one that is going to be caused by Brexit, there are no alternative institutional nets to save the eggs from breaking.

Notes

1. It should be noted that Czechia proposed other projects in the second round of PESCO and was successful to get one of them approved.

List of interviews

- Interview #1; Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Czech Republic; Prague, 21 May 2018.
Interview #2; Ministry of Defence of the Czech Republic; Prague, 24 May 2018.
Interview #3; Office of the Government of the Czech Republic; Prague, 25 May 2018.
Interview #4; Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Czech Republic; Prague, 29 May 2018.
Interview #5; Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Czech Republic; Prague, 27 July 2018.

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